

Complexes of rhodium(III), palladium(II) and platinum(II) with 2-(2'-pyridyl)benzthiazole

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Complexes of Rh^{III}, Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} with 2-(2'-pyridyl)benzthiazole (PBT) of compositions (PBTH)₂[RhCl₅H₂O], [Rh(PBT)₂X₂]X, [Rh(PBT)X₂]ClO₄ (X = Cl, Br, I, NCS or NO₂) and [M(PBT)X₂] (M = Pd^{II} or Pt^{II} and X = Cl, Br, I, NCS or NO₂) have been prepared.

In pursuance of our work on complexes of 2-(2'-pyridyl)benzimidazole and related ligands¹ present paper reports the complexes of Rh^{III}, Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} with 2-(2'-pyridyl)benzthiazole (PBT).

Result and Discussion

The complexes (Table 1) have poor solubility in water but dissolve appreciably in ethanol, dioxane and DMF. The DMF solution of the Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} complexes are non-conducting while the Rh^{III} complexes [Rh(PBT)₂X₂]X display conductance values (70–80 Ω⁻¹ mol⁻¹ cm²) for 1:1 electrolyte. All the complexes are diamagnetic suggesting square-planar structure for the Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} complexes while octahedral geometry for the Rh^{III} complexes. Electronic spectra of ligand in ethanol displays a strong band at 320 nm (ε_{max} = 12300) attributable to π-π* transition. The electronic absorption spectra of [Rh(PBT)₂I₂]I in ethanol (Table 1) display electronic transitions at 390 and 490 nm attributable to ¹A_{1g} → ¹T_{1g} and → ¹T_{2g} transitions.

The reflectance spectra of the complexes display a shoulder at 340–430 nm attributable to transition A_{1g} → A_{2g} for planar Pt^{II} and transition A_{1g} → B_{1g} for the Pd^{II} complexes². The band at 325–360 nm in the Rh^{III} diacido complexes [Rh(PBT)₂X₂]X (X = Cl or NCS) is assigned to ¹A_{1g} → ¹T_{2g} transition in octahedral field. The band at 390 and 500 nm in the diiodo complex is attributed to ¹A_{1g} → ¹T_{1g} and ¹A_{1g} → ¹T_{2g} transitions, respectively^{3,4}.

The NMR spectrum (CDCl₃) of ligand shows phenyl and pyridyl ring signals at δ 6.8–7.4 (4H, m, ArH) and 7.6–8.2 (4H, m, pyH), respectively. The complexes have poor solubility in CDCl₃, however, [Rh(PBT)₂I₂]I and [Pd(PBT)I₂]

are slightly soluble, enough for recording spectra. These complexes show signals at δ 7.1–7.6 (4H, m, ArH) and 7.8–8.4 (4H, m, pyH). The down-field shift of proton signals indicates bonding of the ligand to metal atom. From NMR spectra no specific information could be drawn as no specific position of neighbouring proton signal adjacent to donor atoms could be located.

The IR spectrum of ligand displays bands at 112 (C=N) and 720 cm⁻¹ (C-S-C). The ν_{C-S-C} vibration is not affected in the complexes, indicating that sulfur is not involved in coordination. The ν_{C=N} vibration shifts to lower frequency in the complexes by 10–15 cm⁻¹, suggesting involvement of nitrogen in coordination⁴. The pyridine ring breathing mode of vibration in the ligand is located at 972 cm⁻¹, which is raised by 10–20 cm⁻¹ in the complexes, indicating the coordination of pyridine ring nitrogen⁴. [M(PBT)(NCS)₂] (M = Pd^{II} or Pt^{II}) and [Rh(PBT)₂(NCS)₂]ClO₄ display bands at 2103–2112 (C≡N), 790–830 (C=S) and 480–495 cm⁻¹ (δ NCS) suggesting N bonding of thiocyanate⁵. [M(PBT)₂(NO₂)₂] (M = Pd^{II} or Pt^{II}) and [Rh(PBT)₂(NO₂)₂]ClO₄ display bands around 1416, 1392 (ν_{as}NO₂), 1320 (ν_sNO₂) and 815 cm⁻¹ (δ ONO) (split band), indicating coordination of NO₂ through N atom.

Table 1. Analytical and spectral data of the complexes

Compd./ Colour	Metal % : λ _{max} (nm) Found/ (Calcd.)	Assignment
[LH ₂ (RhCl ₅)H ₂ O] Pink	14.32 (14.20)	
[RhL ₂ Cl ₂]Cl Cream	15.91 (16.25)	325 ^a , 360 ^b CT + ¹ A _{1g} → ¹ T _{2g}
[RhL ₂ Br ₂]Br Cream	13.81 (13.42)	

Table-1 (contd.)

[RhL ₂ I]	12.61	385, 500 ^a	CT + ¹ A _{1g} → ¹ T _{1g} → ¹ T _{2g}
Brown	(12.73)	390, 490 ^b	CT + ¹ A _{1g} → ¹ T _{1g} → ¹ T _{2g}
[RhL ₂ (NO ₂) ₂]	15.61		
NO ₂	(15.47)		
Cream			
[RhL ₂ (NCS) ₂]	14.51	328 ^a	CT + n-π*
NCS	(14.68)	350 ^b	¹ A _{1g} → ¹ T _{2g}
Yellow			
[RhL ₂ (NSC) ₂]	14.05		
ClO ₄	(13.86)		
Yellow			
[RhL ₂ (NO ₂) ₂]	14.44		
ClO ₄	(14.32)		
Cream			
[PdLCl ₂]	27.11	320 ^a	CT + ¹ A _{1g} → ¹ B _{1g}
Cream	(27.33)	380 ^b	¹ A _{1g} → ¹ B _{1g}
[PdLBr ₂]	21.41		
Cream	(21.56)		
[PdLi ₂]	18.41	430 ^b	¹ A _{1g} → ¹ B _{1g}
Yellow	(18.59)		
[PdL(NCS) ₂]	23.78	360 ^b	¹ A _{1g} → ¹ B _{1g}
Yellow	(23.68)		
[PdL(NO ₂) ₂]	24.81		
Cream	(25.07)		
[PtCl ₂]	40.18	325 ^a	CT + n-π*
Cream	(40.85)	350 ^b	¹ A _{1g} → ¹ A _{2g}
[PtLi ₂]	29.13	330, 390 ^a	CT + n-π*
Yellow	(29.51)	390 ^b	¹ A _{1g} → ¹ A _{2g}
[PtL(NCS) ₂]	38.86	325 ^a	CT + n-π*
Yellow	(39.08)	360 ^b	¹ A _{1g} → ¹ A _{2g}
[PtL(NO ₂) ₂]	31.10		
White	(31.28)		

^a In aethanol. ^b Reflectance.

Experimental

PBT was prepared by reported method⁶. Rhodium(III) chloride hydrated, palladium(II) chloride and chloroplatinic acid (Johnson Mathey) were used. Chloroplatinic acid was reduced to PtCl₂ by hydrazine hydrochloride⁷.

(PBTH)₂ [RhCl₅H₂O]: Rhodium(III) chloride (0.001 mol) dissolved in 4 N HCl (30 ml) was treated with hot ethanolic solution (20 ml) of PBT (0.002 mol) when brick-red crystalline precipitate separated. It was allowed to stand at room temperature and the resulting solid was washed with ethanol and dried over CaCl₂, yield 90%.

[Rh(PBT)₂Cl₂]Cl: (PBTH)₂RhCl₅H₂O (1.0 g) dissolved in aqueous ethanol (30 ml) or a mixture of aqueous

ethanolic solution (1%; 30 ml) of Rh^{III} chloride and PBT (0.50 g) was refluxed on a steam bath for 3 h, when cream coloured precipitate separated. The resulting solid was washed with ethanol and dried at 80°, yield 95%.

[Rh(PBT)₂X₂]X (X = Br, I, NCS or NO₂): [Rh(PBT)₂Cl₂]Cl (0.5 g) was suspended in water (100 ml) and refluxed with sodium or potassium salt (2.5 g) of appropriate anion for 6 h on a steam-bath. The refluxate was concentrated on a steam-bath to 30 ml and the resulting solid was washed with water and a little ethanol and dried as above. The perchlorate salt was obtained on digesting the above product with (N)HClO₄ and (N)NaClO₄ solution in aqueous ethanol.

[M(PBT)Cl₂] (M = Pd^{II} or Pt^{II}): An aqueous ethanolic solution of the metal chloride (1.5 g in 50 ml 50% ethanol) as refluxed with ethanolic solution of 1:1 molar proportion of ligand for 2 h. The complexes separated gradually in hot on concentrating the refluxate to a small volume. The resulting solid was washed with water and a little ethanol and dried as above.

[M(PBT)X₂] (M = Pd^{II} or Pt^{II} and X = Br, I, NCS or NO₂): These complexes were obtained by metathesis reaction. Dichloro complex (0.5 g) was refluxed with five-fold excess of K-salts of bromide, iodide, thiocyanide or nitrite in aqueous ethanol (30 ml) for 3–5 h and the refluxate concentrated to a small volume when diacido complexes separated. The resulting solid was washed with ethanol and dried as above.

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